

The Influence of Locus of Control and Providing Incentives for Employee Performance Through Motivation for Sales Generalists PT. Bank Mandiri Cluster Jember

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Abstract- Employee performance is an important factor in determining the success of an organization. There are various factors that influence employee performance, one of which is motivation. Motivation is an urge or desire that directs someone to take action. Locus of control is a person's belief about the extent to which he believes that he can control the results of his actions. Individuals with an internal locus of control believe that they can control the outcomes of their actions, whereas individuals with an external locus of control believe that the outcomes of their actions are determined by factors outside their control. Several studies have been conducted examining the relationship between Locus of Control and performance. However, a few things shows success Sales Generalist PT. Bank Mandiri Cluster Jember . The research results have a big influence on employee performance assessment . PT. Bank Mandiri Cluster Jember tries to measure employee performance from Locus of Control and Providing Incentives through Motivation . This decision making is based on existing theory. Even the role of Locus of Control is expected to be able to make PT Sales Generalists. Bank Mandiri Cluster Jember is getting better at achieving its targets.

Keywords: Locus of Control, Providing Incentives, Employee Performance, Motivation

INTRODUCTION

Bank Mandiri Cluster Jember is a regional regional office whose activities include lending, assisted by productive sales generalists and consumptive sales generalists. Productive sales generalists are officers who help carry out special consumer credit distribution, such as people's business credit (KUR) and micro business credit (KUM). Where, people's business credit (KUR) is a credit distribution program from the government, while micro business credit is a regular credit distribution program from Bank Mandiri. Consumptive sales generalists are officers who help carry out credit distribution specifically for employees, both civil servants and private employees. Bank Mandiri in each regional/regional office is divided into several area offices and micro clusters .

Phenomenon shows that the increasing business competition in the banking world means that the targets and responsibilities of productive sales generalists and consumptive sales generalists also increase, this makes their focus divided and ultimately affects their work achievements so that the incentives they receive are not comparable. Decreased motivation is also one of the triggers that causes a decline in employee performance , with thereby in running the organization's business is felt need to provide reciprocity for the contributions made employees in carrying out their duties to achieve the expected goals. So satisfaction Work employee can created with the best so moral Work, dedication And work motivation employees increase. Sales people Productive generalists and consumptive sales generalists are required to continue to meet the targets given by management, both regular business targets and digital-based business targets, but it cannot be denied that due to the limited time and energy they have, many of them lose locus of control and decrease motivation . Work. As is known, the incentives received by productive sales generalists and consumptive sales generalists are based on targets being met. Giving incentive can increase performance Work And motivating employee. By Because That, attention organization or companies towards providing incentives rationally and fairly is indispensable. When employees view incentives inadequate then performance employee tend to decrease.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Locus of controls according to Rotter (in Ghuftron et al 2011) stated that locus of control is a person's belief about how much control they have over what happens in their life. The control in question includes daily decisions, events (the effects of decisions), and life as a whole. The concept of locus of control is quite simple, namely that a person's behavior is influenced by various types of punishment and rewards. Locus of control can influence responses to events in life and also motivation to take action. The research gap was found in research conducted by Ahmad Robith Fuady (2020) stating that the locus of control has no effect on performance. Research gaps were also found in research conducted by Sogia Ramdani (2019) stating that locus of control has no effect on motivation. Thus, locus of control is an individual's belief in the main causes of behavior and events in his life.

Incentives are one of the incentives or rewards given to employees and have nothing to do with wages or salaries (Sumbangsih & Malta, 2013). If the incentives received are not based on exceeding the specified target, but on an individual basis, then employee

performance will not increase. The main objective of providing incentives is to give full responsibility to employees and motivate employees to increase productivity and lead to organizational goals so that companies/organizations will be able to increase profits (Ardian, 2019). Research gaps were also found in research conducted by Venny Ferari Veronica (2019) stating that incentives have no effect on motivation. A research gap was also found in research conducted by Cornelius Pasaribu (2020) stating that incentives have no effect on employee performance.

According to Simanjuntak (2015:1) performance is the achievement of top results implementation of certain tasks. Company performance is the level of achievement results in order to realize company goals. Performance is a universal concept that is effective operations of an organization and its employees based on standards and criteria which has been previously determined. The organization is basically run by humans, then actual performance is human behavior in playing the roles they carry out in an organization to meet the behavioral standards that have been set in order to produce the desired results and actions. The research gap was found in research conducted by Achmad Alfarizi (2022) stating that motivation has no effect on performance. A research gap was also found in research conducted by Galaxy Mustofa (2022) stating that motivation has no effect on performance. Research gaps were also found in research conducted by Ilvia Restu Utami (2023) stating that motivation has no effect on performance. The existence of this gap causes researchers to need to carry out research again to produce different findings or findings that are consistent with the research that has been carried out .

According to Hasibuan (2018) , Berelson and Steiner (2010) motivation is the provision of driving force that create excitement Work somebody, so that they Want to Work together, work effectively, and are integrated with all their efforts to achieve satisfaction. The process of generating a person's motivation is a combination of the concepts of need, drive, goal and reward. Motivation itself is a driving force in a person's heart to do or achieve a goal. The research gap found in research conducted by Kusumastuti (2019) stated that motivation cannot mediate the influence of locus of control on performance. Research gaps were also found in research conducted by Venny Ferari Veronica (2019) stating that motivation unable to mediate the influence of locus of control on performance .

Research Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Concept Framework

DISCUSSION

This article discusses variables that influence employee performance. Based on references book Which There is as well as study previous is known that Lots factor Which influential in a way positive impact on employee performance. Some of these factors include Locus of Control , Providing Incentives and Work Motivation .

Influence Locus of Control on Work Motivation _ _Employees at Sales General is PT. Mandiri Bank Clusters Jember.

Locus of control according to Retnoningsih, (2013) is a measure that shows how a person is looking at the possibility of a relationship between the actions carried out and the consequences or consequences the results obtained, so that the locus of control is also called the control center where the individual Certain that they is determiner of fate themselves. The results of Moh's research. Abi Rafdianto (2022) shows that Locus of Control has a positive and significant effect on employee work motivation. These results indicate that the greater the locus of control in work, the greater the employee's work motivation.

H1: Locus of control influential significant to employee work motivation Sales Generalist PT. Bank Mandiri Cluster Jember .

The Effect of Providing Incentives to Employee Work Motivation at Sales Generalist PT. Bank Mandiri Cluster Jember.

According to Simamora (2015), incentives are everything that is received by the person employee as their contribution to organization, incentives are calculated based on evaluation that job intended For get giving incentive Which approach appropriateness And justice. Abdul Aziz's research results (2019) show that providing incentives has a positive and significant

effect on employee work motivation. These results indicate that the greater the incentives provided in their work, the greater the employee's work motivation.

H2: Providing incentives influential significant to m work motivation.

Influence Locus of Control to Performance Employee on Sales Generalist PT. Bank Mandiri Cluster Jember.

Locus of controls is dimensions personality Which explain that individual behave influenced expectation about himself , Rotter (in Ghufuron et al 2011)state that locus of controls is description confidence individual regarding the source of determinants of behavior which has four aspects underlying locus of control namely potential behavior, expectations, reinforcers, And atmosphere psychological. Anak Agung Ayu Ratih Radityastuti's research results (2019) show that locus of control has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. These results indicate that the greater the locus of control in work, the greater the employee's performance.

H3: Locus of control influential significant to performance employee.

Influence Providing Incentives to Performance Employee on Sales Generalist PT. Bank Mandiri Cluster Jember.

(Widakdo et al. ,2022) says that incentives are a form of direct payment based or directly related to performance and profits obtained. Matter This shows that there is an influence significant between incentives with performance employee. Results study Suriani (2020) shows Providing incentives has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. These results show that the more big Providing incentives in their work will improve the employee's performance.

H4: Providing incentives influential significant to performance employee.

Influence Motivation to Performance Employee on Sales Generalist PT. Bank Mandiri Cluster Jember.

Motivation according to Stephen P. Robbins (2013), define motivation as process Which explain intensity, direction, And perseverance somebody individual For reach the goal is a necessity Which push deed toward something objective certain ones Motive is what motivates an individual to do so do reach objective certain. Robith Abdillah's research results (2022) show that motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. These results show that the greater the motivation in work, the greater the employee's performance.

H5: Motivation influential significant to employee performance .

Influence Locus of Control to Performance Employee through Work Motivation Sales Generalist PT. Bank Mandiri Cluster Jember

Rahmat Suhadi's research results (2021) concluded that the mediating role of the work motivation variable was able to increase the strength of the locus of control variable on employee performance by 0.149. It shows that the influence of locus of control on work motivation is 14.9 % , so that there is an indirect influence between the locus of control variable on employee performance through motivation which is in the strong category or in other words motivation is able to mediate locus of control on employee performance.

H6: Locus of control matters significant to employee performance through work motivation .

The Effect of Providing Incentives on Performance Employee through Work Motivation _ _ on Sales Generalist PT. Bank Mandiri Cluster Jember

The research results of Fransisca Viana Putri Trisnaningrum (2021) concluded that the mediating role of the work motivation variable was able to increase the strength of the incentive variable on employee performance by 0.324. Shows that the influence of providing incentives on work motivation is 32.4 % , so there is an indirect influence between the variable providing incentives on employee performance through motivation which is in the strong category or in other words motivation is able to mediate the provision of incentives on employee performance.

H7: Providing incentives significant effect on performance employee through work motivation.

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Plan

Design study is something proposal For solve problem And is plan activities created _ researcher For solve problem , so will appropriate valid data is obtained with objective research . Type study This is study quantitative with method analysis partial least squares (PLS). Research data is primary data and secondary . Study This is explanatory research that is based testing _ on study theoretical And empirical .

Population and Sample

Population in study This is all over employee sales generalist PT. Bank Independent Clusters Jember which amounted to 89 people. Sample _ in study This is sample fed up or method census that is technique determination sample when all member population used as sample . (Sugiyono , 2014:85). So all over sales generalist PT. Bank Mandiri Clusters Jember will be respondents in this research.

Sources of Data

Type of data used in study This is nature quantitative namely statistical data shaped the numbers , okay in a way direct dug from results study nor results qualitative data management into quantitative data . Data sources used in study This is Primary Data and

Secondary Data

CONCLUSION

Human resource management is an important thing for every organization to pay attention to. Quality and skilled human resources can increase organizational productivity. Locus of control and providing incentives have a positive influence on employee motivation. Employee motivation has a positive influence on employee performance. Organizations can improve employee performance by paying attention to these two factors, namely locus of control and providing incentives.

In the increasingly developing business world, PT. Bank Mandiri Cluster Jember needs superior human resources in the field of work, especially in the performance of its employees. With increasingly strong levels of competition, human resources have become the main object in overcoming threats and opportunities. For this reason, further research needs to be carried out to determine the influence of locus of control and Providing Incentives for Employee Performance Through Motivation for Sales Generalists PT. Bank Mandiri Cluster Jember.

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